

Interplay of Fluid Modes and Aerodynamic Mistuning in Transonic Fan Shock Buffet

Jyoti Ranjan Majhi

Kartik Venkatraman

*Department of Aerospace Engineering
Indian Institute of Science
Bangalore, India.*

*Name of Corresponding Author: **Kartik Venkatraman** Email of*

Corresponding Author: kartik@iisc.ac.in

OBJECTIVES

Axial flow fan, Transonic buffet, Unsteady Aerodynamics, URANS, Spectral Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (SPOD), Aerodynamic mistuning.

BACKGROUND AND INTRODUCTION

Shock wave-boundary layer interaction over airfoils operating in transonic flow incites aerodynamic instabilities involving boundary layer separation. At certain flow conditions, the boundary layer separates and reattaches intermittently which causes the foot of the part-chord shock present over the airfoil surface to move back and forth in the stream-wise direction. The resulting shock oscillation is self-sustained and is also known as transonic shock buffet. An airfoil featuring such shock oscillation experiences unsteady air loads that vary in time as the shock position changes in time. These unsteady loads can trigger structural vibration of the airfoil, also known as transonic buffeting, which can lead to failure of the structure through fatigue. The transonic shock buffet and buffeting phenomena are prevalent not only in aircraft wings but also in gas turbine engine fan and compressor blades.

A review of the literature over the past two decades suggests substantial research on shock wave-boundary layer interaction

and shock buffet in aircraft wings (1; 2; 3; 4; 5). Lee (6), Giannelis (7), and Gao (8) have presented elaborate reviews of the transonic buffet phenomenon containing experimental and numerical findings on fixed wings. The most common model of describing the buffet phenomenon is due to Lee (1; 6). From the study of shock oscillations over a supercritical airfoil, Lee proposed a buffet model based on a feedback loop of shock-induced downstream-propagating pressure perturbation waves and upstream-propagating disturbances resulting from the interaction of the downstream-propagating waves with large vortical structures present in the vicinity of the trailing edge of the airfoil. Deck (9), Jacquin, *et al* (2) and Hartmann, *et al* (3) have further bolstered the buffet model proposed by Lee (1). Deck's study on a supercritical airfoil, using a zonal detached eddy simulation (ZDES), upholds Lee's hypothesis on the origin of upstream-propagating disturbances resulting from acoustic radiation due to the impingement of large-scale structures on the upper surface of the airfoil in the vicinity of the trailing edge, and these upstream-propagating waves can regenerate an instability leading to a feedback mechanism. Jacquin, *et al* (2) conducted wind tunnel experiments on a OAT15 airfoil in order to study shock-boundary layer interactions and associated shock motion. They propose a model similar to that of Lee to a large extent, from their wind tunnel experiments on a supercritical airfoil, but their measurements suggest the possibility of acoustic disturbances generated near the trailing edge not only propagating upstream on the suction side towards the shock foot, but also that these acoustic disturbances propagating in the upstream direction along the pressure surface and then turning around the leading edge to excite the shock on the suction surface. They also discuss the 2D versus 3D nature of transonic shock buffet since their measurements and visualization suggest the possibility of both. Hartmann, *et al* (3) experimentally investigated shock oscillations due to shock-boundary layer interactions over a supercritical airfoil in transonic flow. From estimation of spatio-temporal correlations of flow quantities obtained using the experimental data, it corroborates the acoustic feedback mechanism for shock oscillation proposed by (6) with certain modification to the distance the

upstream-propagating wave travels.

There are other approaches to predict and understand transonic buffet in literature. According to Crouch, *et al* (10), transonic buffet is a global instability which can be derived from a global linear stability analysis. Poplinger, *et al* (11) presented modal analysis of buffet flow over a supercritical airfoil, using proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) and dynamic mode decomposition (DMD), finding coherent structures in buffet flow and showed reconstruction of shock buffet using minimal number of modes. Using large eddy simulations (LES), Dandois *et al* (12) identified laminar buffet characterized by a separation bubble breathing phenomenon associated with a vortex shedding mechanism as opposed to turbulent buffet which features intermittent boundary layer separation and reattachment between the shock and the trailing edge. Moise *et al* (13) demonstrated modal decomposition and reconstruction of laminar transonic buffet on an infinite wing using spectral proper orthogonal decomposition (SPOD) of LES simulation results. While the wave propagation method has been widely used to explain the mechanism of shock buffet usually by quantifying the stream-wise wave propagation speeds, with the use of modal analysis techniques one can visualize coherent structures of specific fluid modes.

There is relatively meager literature on transonic shock buffet in the realm of turbomachinery. Strazisar (14) conducted experimental investigation to understand shock structure and shock motion of a transonic fan using laser anemometry. Strazisar observed a bow shock, and at certain operating conditions, a passage shock. Strazisar also reports observing sustained shock motion whose amplitude was about 3–4% of fan chord at certain operating points on the fan performance map. However, it fell short in describing essential attributes of the shock oscillation like the oscillation frequency.

In recent times, transonic buffet and buffeting phenomena were investigated in a compressor cascade (non-rotating) by Klinner, *et al* (15) and Klinner, *et al* (16). Klinner *et al* (15) present a very detailed description of the shock structure that contains a bow shock, a lambda passage shock, and lip shock. They report that the transonic buffet flow excited flexural vibration mode of the blade, that is, buffeting. As far as the mechanism of transonic buffet in their cascade is concerned, Klinner *et al* (16) report it to be remarkably different than that proposed by Lee (1) for fixed wings. Their experiment on the compressor cascade suggests a feedback mechanism between a region downstream just next to the foot of the shock and a region upstream of the shock front. Besides these experimental investigations, there are hardly any numerical attempts to investigate transonic shock buffet in turbomachinery.

In our previous work (17), shock buffet at two operating points—near design mass flow and near stall—on the performance map for an axial flow fan, was numerically captured and the driving mechanism of buffet was elucidated using wave propagation analysis. A feedback loop consisting of upstream and

downstream propagating pressure perturbation waves estimated using spatio-temporal correlation of fluctuating flow quantities was found to be driving the shock oscillation.

The alternating shrinking/stretching of circumferential spacing of adjacent rotor blades seen here is known to alter the aeroelastic stability of fans as reported by (18; 19). Alternating mis-staggering of the fan blades is shown to influence the aerodynamic performance (20; 21). Besides, blade-to-blade shock detachment distance variability and mis-staggering are known to generate buzz-saw noise (22). Lu *et al* (21) report occurrence of alternating mis-staggering in close proximity to the design point which is the case here also. Further, Lu *et al* (21) attribute the mechanism of this phenomenon to variable shock positioning on alternate passages which is also reported in detail in this work. In addition, (21) state that alternating mis-staggering can be accompanied by a traveling disturbance around the annulus, which has been reported for the fan configuration investigated in this work using spectral proper orthogonal decomposition of buffet flow.

In literature, alternating mis-staggering is attributed to manufacturing tolerances, and wear and tear. These triggers are of more qualitative nature and cannot be exactly quantified, and consequently, there is no profound correlation of these with alternating mis-staggering; on that account, hypothetical geometric mistuning is employed to reproduce alternating mis-staggering. In contrast, in this work, alternating mis-staggering is shown to be resulting from the aerodynamic mistuning arising of transonic shock buffet for this fan consisting of a set of tuned blades. Therefore, transonic shock buffet can be a formidable trigger to alternating mis-staggering of blades. This aerodynamic mistuning of fan blades resulting from the buffet flow can influence the aeroelastic stability, aerodynamic performance, aeroacoustic behaviour, and high cycle fatigue life of the fan.

In this present work, first, the modal characteristics of the unsteady flow field featuring shock buffet are investigated using spectral proper orthogonal decomposition (SPOD) to discern the buffet mechanism and to visualize any evidence for the feedback loop of pressure perturbation waves reported earlier. Subsequently, the structural implication of the time-varying air loads in a buffet flow field is evaluated by assessing the aeromechanical response of the fan following its modal structural dynamic characterization.

METHODOLOGIES

The NASA rotor 67 (23; 24) is the chosen test case for carrying out the investigations of this work. The rotor 67 is a transonic fan with 22 low aspect ratio blades. It has a design rotational speed of 16043 rev/min, a design pressure ratio of 1.63, and a design mass flow rate of 33.25 kg/s. More details of the test case can be found in (23), where 1-D performance parameters were evaluated and reported, too. The basic design specifications are summarized in Table 1. The meridional view of the

FIGURE 1: Meridional view of rotor 67 and aerodynamic survey locations (23).

FIGURE 2: Full-annulus computational grid.

rotor 67 is shown in Fig. 1 along with the aerodynamic survey locations—AERO STATIONS 1 and 2—(23). Shock oscillations were reported on this configuration from experimental (14) and numerical investigations (17). In the present work, the mechanism of shock oscillation is investigated by studying the behavior of coherent flow structures in a buffet flow using SPOD, followed by assessment of the aeromechanical response of the fan to the unsteady air loads arising of shock buffet.

The fluid flow solution was obtained using a cell-vertex based finite volume method using the SU2 (25; 26) suite of CFD codes. The reader is referred to Ref. (17) for the details of the governing equations, flow numerical schemes, turbulence model, boundary conditions, and the computational grid used. A picture of the full-annulus grid is shown in Fig. 2. The grid consisted of about 18 million cells and featured y^+ values less than 1 on solid surfaces. Note that the rotor 67 also features a tip gap of 0.001016 m

TABLE 1: NASA rotor 67 specifications

Number of blades	22
Rotational speed (design)	16043 rev/min
Mass flow rate (design)	33.25 kg/s
Pressure ratio (design)	1.63
Rotor tip speed (design)	429 m/s
Tip clearance (design)	0.001016 m
Inlet tip relative Mach number (design)	1.38
Aspect ratio (average span/root axial chord)	1.56
Hub/tip radius ratio at inlet	0.375
Hub/tip radius ratio at exit	0.478
Solidity at tip	1.29
Solidity at hub	3.11
Tip diameter at inlet	0.514 m
Tip diameter at exit	0.485 m

which is not shown in this picture but is taken care of in the computational grid, more details of which can be found in Ref. (17).

Roe's upwind scheme (27) was used for discretizing the convective fluxes and second-order MUSCL reconstruction was realized using the van Albada limiter (28). Flow gradients were calculated with a Green-Gauss method for evaluating the viscous fluxes. The source terms were approximated using piece-wise constant reconstruction within each of the finite volume cells. The Euler implicit method was used for temporal discretization and integration. The generalized minimum residual (GMRES) method based on a Krylov subspace involving Arnoldi iteration was used. The linear solver was pre-conditioned using an incomplete Lower-Upper (ILU) scheme. A Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number of 20 was used for steady flow simulations. For the unsteady flow simulations, a dual time-stepping technique was used, wherein the unsteady problem was transformed into a steady-state problem at each physical time step which was then solved using the methodology for steady flows.

For turbulence closure, the Spalart-Allmaras (SA)(29) turbulence model with Edwards and Chandra's correction (30) was used. The standard SA model maintains the log-layer behavior of the strain-rate norm all the way to the wall and displays singular behaviour for it in the near-wall region. With alternative formulations for the strain-rate norm and the argument of the wall-blockage function, the version of SA turbulence model by Edwards and Chandra gives a more stable way of accounting for the behavior of the strain-rate norm in the laminar sub-layer with

better convergence when compared with the standard SA model.

The unsteady flow field featuring shock buffet is investigated using the SPOD method of modal decomposition and reconstruction. SPOD is an effective method for extracting coherent structures from statistically stationary flows (31; 32; 33). It is a special form of the standard POD method that evolves in both space and time, unlike POD which is a space-only method. According to (31), SPOD modes can be also shown to be optimally averaged DMD modes obtained from an ensemble DMD problem for statistically stationary flows. Thus, for statistically stationary flows, SPOD combines the advantages of DMD in terms of expressing temporal correlation among the resulting structures, with the optimal spatial attributes associated with POD. The SPOD decomposes the flow into mutually orthogonal modes at distinct frequencies and ranks them in order of spectral energy.

The key steps of the SPOD algorithm used are as follows.

1. A time series of snapshots \mathbf{q}_k is assembled in a matrix form as

$$\mathbf{Q} = [\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \dots, \mathbf{q}_{N_t}] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N_t} \quad (1)$$

where M is number of grid points times number of flow variables and N_t is the total number of snapshots.

2. Cross-spectral densities (CSD) are estimated using Welch's method (34). The matrix \mathbf{Q} , containing the spatio-temporal data is partitioned into N_b number of smaller, possibly overlapping, blocks as

$$\mathbf{Q}^{(n)} = [\mathbf{q}_1^{(n)}, \mathbf{q}_2^{(n)}, \dots, \mathbf{q}_{N_f}^{(n)}] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N_f}; \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N_b \quad (2)$$

where N_f is the number of snapshots in each block. For each block discrete Fourier transform (DFT) is carried out.

$$\hat{\mathbf{Q}}^{(n)} = [\hat{\mathbf{q}}_1^{(n)}, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_2^{(n)}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{N_f}^{(n)}] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N_f} \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^{(n)}$, for $k = 1, 2, \dots, N_f$ and $n = 1, 2, \dots, N_b$, represents the n^{th} realization of the Fourier mode for the k^{th} discrete frequency f_k .

For each frequency $k = 1, 2, \dots, N_f$, assemble the matrix $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{f_k} = [\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^{(1)}, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^{(2)}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^{(N_b)}]$ of Fourier realizations from the k^{th} column of each $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}^{(n)}$. The CSD tensor for the k^{th} frequency f_k then can be written as

$$\mathbf{S}_{f_k} = \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{f_k} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{f_k}^* \quad (4)$$

3. The following eigenvalue problem is solved

$$\mathbf{S}_{f_k} \mathbf{W} \boldsymbol{\psi}_{f_k} = \boldsymbol{\psi}_{f_k} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{f_k} \quad (5)$$

to get the SPOD modes for the k^{th} frequency given by the columns of $\boldsymbol{\psi}_{f_k}$ ranked according to their corresponding eigenvalues $\lambda_k^{(n)}$ given by the diagonal matrix $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{f_k}$. Here \mathbf{W} is an appropriate weight matrix for scaling various flow variables. For compressible flows, a norm based on the derivation of total small disturbance energy by (35) is widely used for defining the weight matrix. More details on the choice of norms used for various flow types can be found in (31; 32).

The flow field for any discrete frequency f_k can be reconstructed using SPOD modes in the time domain as follows.

$$\mathbf{q}_k(\mathbf{x}, t) = \bar{\mathbf{q}} + \sum_{i=1}^{NMODE} \text{Re}\{A_i \boldsymbol{\psi}_{f_k}(\mathbf{x}, f_k) e^{i2\pi f_k t}\} \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{q}}$ represents the mean of flow quantities, \mathbf{x} represents the spatial co-ordinates, t is the time, $NMODE$ is number of SPOD modes considered for modal reconstruction and A_i is a suitable expansion coefficient for which more details can be found in (36).

MAIN RESULTS

Shock buffet was captured at two operating points on the fan performance map—near design mass flow rate and towards stall—with URANS simulations using the full-annulus model, the details of which can be found in Ref. (17). For the operating point near to design mass flow, shock excursion of about 1.8% chord was seen near the foot of the shock while a shock excursion of 1.01% with a buffet frequency of 385 Hz was estimated from the pressure signals on the blade surface. For the operating point towards stall, a shock excursion of 1.6% was observed near the shock foot while an excursion of 0.95% chord was estimated from the pressure signals on the blade surface with a frequency of 433 Hz. Further, shocks in adjacent passages were reported to move in an almost out-of-phase manner with respect to each other.

An instantaneous snap of static pressure contours with projected relative Mach lines at 30%, 50%, 70% and 90% span-wise sections over blade suction surface obtained from the unsteady simulation at the operating point near design mass flow is shown in Fig. 3. From the animation of such static pressure contours with projected relative Mach lines over time, shock buffet is visualized at all the span-wise stations considered,

Modal Analysis

Modal analysis of the unsteady flow solution featuring shock buffet near design mass flow is carried out in order to understand

FIGURE 3: Static pressure contours over blade suction surface with projected relative Mach lines at 30%, 50%, 70%, and 90% span-wise sections.

the underlying physics of buffet flow over gas turbine engine fan blades. We have investigated fluid modes in the stream-wise direction, in the circumferential direction upstream and downstream of the blade row, and along the span of a blade as described in the following sections.

Fluid modes in stream-wise and circumferential directions Unsteady data of static pressure and relative Mach number at a representative span-wise location of 70% from the whole annulus model, containing flow solutions over all blades, are processed for SPOD. All the results presented in this subsection correspond to this representative span-wise location of 70%. The data set consists of 1500 snapshots sampled at every five time steps used for the URANS simulation ($\approx 5 \times 10^{-5}$ s). The data was partitioned into blocks containing 200 snapshots each. With an overlap of 100 snapshots, 14 realizations were estimated.

For compressible flows, the total small disturbance energy formulation for defining the SPOD norm considers the fluctuating components of the flow quantities—density, three velocity components, and temperature (35; 32). However, for fans (and compressors) pressure fluctuation is of primary importance, and in addition, the relative Mach number variation also needs to be captured in order to visualize shock oscillations. Defining an appropriate norm with the variables of our interest is ambiguous. Nevertheless, variance of data of individual equally important signals can be studied to interpret useful information about coherent flow structures, without any loss of generality (32; 36). Hence, here we are processing the pressure signals and the rela-

tive Mach number signals individually for spectral decomposition without delving into defining a befitting norm.

FIGURE 4: SPOD mode energy spectra from M_{rel} signals

The SPOD mode energy spectra of relative Mach number signals are presented in Fig. 4. The mode energy spectra may not be prominently low rank but the mode energy for the first mode is significantly higher than the subsequent modes, and the buffet frequency of 385 Hz is captured as the dominant frequency besides smaller peaks observed at harmonics of it. Contours of mean relative Mach number are shown in Fig. 5a and the spatial structure of the dominant SPOD mode, the first mode, is shown in Fig. 5b which is plotted using the real part of the corresponding SPOD mode. A phase difference of about 180° is evident in the flow structures near the shocks in adjacent passages from the first SPOD mode. We recall here, that in Reference (17), it was reported that shocks in adjacent passages were found to be moving with a phase difference of about 180° .

Figure 6 (right) shows a snap of the relative Mach number contour reconstructed using the mean values and only the SPOD mode with the highest mode energy (mode 1) using Eq. 6. The figure also contains the contours plotted with the raw data (left). The conformance of the reconstructed flow field is ascertained by animating it over several buffet cycles and comparing it with the actual data as shown in the animation included in the presentation. Thus, the most energetic mode alone along with the mean flow is reasonably able to capture the buffet mode and can be considered the most dominant mode contributing to buffet. This gives us confidence that the SPOD algorithm implemented is reasonably accurate.

Figure 7 shows the SPOD mode energy spectra processed

from static pressure signals at the representative span-wise location of 70% from the whole annulus model. The mode energy spectra clearly pick the buffet frequency of 385 Hz besides smaller peaks observed at harmonics of it. Fig. 8 shows the mean pressure field. The dominant SPOD mode is shown in Fig. 9 for different instances of time during a buffet cycle; in the figure T is the buffet period. A phase difference of about 180° (not exactly 180°) in between the flow structures surrounding the shock locations in adjacent passages may be apparent from Fig. 9. Pressure disturbance waves can be seen to propagate circumferentially in spinning direction of the rotor from the spatial flow structures, corresponding to the first SPOD mode, at different instances of time as shown in Fig. 9 (arrows are marked in the figure indicating the direc-

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 5: (a) Mean M_{rel} contours and (b) Most energetic M_{rel} SPOD mode.

FIGURE 6: Relative Mach number contours; left - actual data, right - reconstructed.

FIGURE 7: SPOD mode energy spectra from pressure signals

FIGURE 8: Mean static pressure distribution on all blades at 70% span

tion of travel of the waves) which can be more clearly seen from the animation of the corresponding mode. Pressure disturbances upstream and downstream of the blade row are estimated to propagate in the circumferential direction with a part-speed of about 16% of the fan speed in the spinning direction in this mode. Further, portions of the circumferentially-travelling pressure waves downstream of the blade row are seen to be transforming into upstream-propagating pressure waves within each passage. The buffet mechanism in fixed wings is reported to be resulting from a feedback loop consisting of upstream- and downstream-pressure perturbation waves (1; 6; 9; 3). And, for this fan configuration, (37; 17) have explained the buffet mechanism using upstream- and

FIGURE 9: SPOD mode 1 spatial structures for the whole annulus at different instances during a buffet cycle

downstream-pressure perturbation waves estimated from spatio-temporal correlations of fluctuating components of flow quantities. Therefore, the circumferential pressure waves visualized here through the dominant SPOD mode are integral part of shock buffet mechanism in this turbomachine that are helping the buffet flow sustain.

In order to investigate presence of any downstream-propagating pressure waves, we visualize the dominant SPOD fluid mode more closely within a single passage. Fig. 10 shows spatial flow structures corresponding to the dominant SPOD mode spanning about one pitch from the whole annulus at different instances of time during a buffet cycle and the corresponding animation shown in the presentation. We can clearly see upstream-propagating pressure waves near either surfaces (pres-

FIGURE 10: SPOD mode 1 spatial structures for a single passage at different instances during a buffet cycle

sure and suction) of the blade (directions marked as black arrows). Further, a downstream-propagating pressure wave emanating from the shock front is observed (direction marked as red arrow) near the suction side of the blade surface. In literature (1; 6; 9; 3), the origin of the downstream-propagating pressure wave in fixed wings is attributed to shock-boundary layer interaction and the pressure wave is reported to be initiating from the shock. Although, the current configuration involves substantially more complexity when compared to fixed wings, as it represents rotating blades in internal flow, the physics of shock buffet in it can thus still be explained with the arguments used for explaining the phenomenon over fixed wings. Note that, there was no downstream-propagating pressure wave seen near the pressure side of the blade; this is because of the fact mentioned earlier that downstream-propagating pressure wave appears as a result of shock-boundary layer interaction and there is no shock present on the pressure surface for our case.‘

Fluid modes in radial direction Having observed stream-wise pressure perturbation waves, the key constituents in the broader theory for the shock buffet mechanism over fixed wings (1), and circumferential pressure perturbation waves that form integral part of the wave propagation mechanism specific to this turbomachine, we investigate the presence of any wave propagation in the radial (span-wise) direction of the blades. The static pressure data over a blade surface are processed for modal decomposition as the other variables like velocities or Mach number vanish on the no-slip blade surface.

FIGURE 11: SPOD mode energy spectra from pressure signals on suction surface

FIGURE 12: SPOD mode 1 spatial structures over blade suction surface at different instances during a buffet cycle

Figure 11 shows the mode energy spectra from pressure signals sampled on the suction surface of a blade. The first SPOD mode seems to be substantially dominant and the buffet frequency of 385 Hz appears clearly as the dominant frequency besides peaks at its super-harmonics. Spatial flow structures on the suction surface corresponding to the first mode at various instances of time during a buffet cycle are shown in Fig. 12. Radially-outward moving pressure waves with components in upstream direction are clearly seen to be emanating from the hub downstream of mid-chord which can be visualized more clearly from the video in the presentation. Also downstream-propagating pressure waves are observed emanating from various span-wise shock locations which further support the findings reported at 70% span as presented in the next section.

FIGURE 13: SPOD mode energy spectra from pressure signals on pressure surface

Figure 13 shows the SPOD mode energy spectra from pressure signals sampled on the blade pressure surface. The first

FIGURE 14: SPOD mode 1 spatial structures over blade pressure surface at different instances during a buffet cycle

SPOD mode seems to be the dominant one and the buffet frequency of 385 Hz is clearly picked as the dominant frequency. Figure 14 shows the spatial flow structures corresponding to the first SPOD mode at different instances of time during a buffet cycle. Pressure waves emanating from the hub near the mid-chord location are observed to travel in radial and upstream directions. This finding further supports the reporting of absence of any downstream-propagating pressure waves in the section on stream-wise and circumferential modes.

It is to be noted that the axial (stream-wise) and circumferential flow structures corresponding to the dominant SPOD mode were found to be intertwined, as discussed in the section on stream-wise and circumferential modes, and the radial flow structures corresponding to the dominant SPOD mode are found to exhibit axially-moving pressure waves also, as discussed earlier in this section. These findings suggest substantial interplay of the fluid modes in the three individual directions—axial, radial and circumferential.

Summary

Modal analysis of buffet flow near design mass flow operating point using SPOD clearly captures the buffet frequency. Just the most energetic SPOD mode in addition to the mean flow suffices for reconstruction of the buffet flow. The flow structures near the shocks of adjacent passages corresponding to the dominant SPOD mode are found to be displaying a phase difference of about 180°. Further, pressure disturbances, associated with this SPOD mode, are found to be propagating circumferentially at part-speed of the fan in the spinning direction of the fan, and part of the circumferentially-propagating pressure waves downstream of the blade row is transformed into upstream-propagating waves inside the passages. Apart from the upstream-propagating waves, downstream-propagating pressure waves are also seen emanating from the shock fronts in each passage, and thus the key constituents for the mechanism of shock buffet on fixed wings, that is, stream-wise pressure waves (upstream- and downstream-propagating), are found to be present in the buffet flow for this turbomachine as well. Further, radially-outward moving pressure waves are observed from the dominant SPOD modes of static pressure signals sampled on the blade suction and pres-

sure surfaces. Besides the radial pressure waves, on the suction surface, traces of both upstream- and downstream-propagating pressure waves are seen, whereas on the pressure surface traces of only upstream-propagating pressure waves are seen. The fluid modes in the three directions—axial, radial and circumferential—corresponding to the dominant SPOD mode are found to exhibit substantial interplay.

Aeromechanical Response

A typical aeromechanical response of the fan structure to the time-varying air loads arising of buffet flow is presented here. The buffet flow corresponding to the operating point near to design mass flow of the fan is chosen for the purpose.

In (17), results from unsteady simulations on the full-annulus model of the transonic axial flow fan were presented that show shock excursions up to 1.8% chord with a frequency of 385 Hz at an operating point near design mass flow, and excursions up to 1.6% chord with a frequency of 433 Hz at an operating point towards stall. Significant hysteresis in blade loading is also observed during shock buffet. Shock motions in adjacent passages are found to be almost out-of-phase with respect to each other. The shock oscillations which are essentially initiated from shock-induced boundary layer separation, give rise to time-varying pressure fluctuations on gas turbine fan and compressor blades that can trigger buffeting or blade vibration. Modal analysis of buffet flow near design mass flow operating point using SPOD show that the fluid modes in the three directions—axial, radial and circumferential—corresponding to the dominant SPOD mode are found to exhibit substantial interplay. Further, significant hysteresis in blade loading is also observed during shock buffet. Shock motions in adjacent passages are found to be almost out-of-phase with respect to each other. In this section, the aeromechanical response of the fan structure due to the unsteady aerodynamic loading caused by shock buffet in the axial flow fan is investigated. In order to determine whether the unsteady loads would induce buffeting of the structure, the modal characteristics of the structure were evaluated at first. Subsequently, an appropriate structural response estimation method was adopted to assess the response of the fan structure to an unsteady flow field featuring shock buffet.

Modal analysis

The structural analysis results presented here are calculated using ANSYS Workbench Student software (38). A rotating blade inside a gas turbine engine is pre-stressed with two types of loads—centrifugal load and gas load. For a rotating structure, the centrifugal forces try to further stiffen the structure. The frequency for any particular mode is given as

$$\omega_{rot}^2 = \omega_{nr}^2 + k \Omega^2 \quad (7)$$

TABLE 2: Comparison of first six natural frequencies using three meshes

Mode	Coarse (8145 nodes)		Medium (15560 nodes)		Fine (31823 nodes)
	Frequency [Hz]	% Error w.r.t. Fine	Frequency [Hz]	% Error w.r.t. Fine	Frequency [Hz]
Mode 1	536.74	0.04	536.61	0.01	536.54
Mode 2	1246.2	0.06	1245.7	0.02	1245.4
Mode 3	1778.9	0.08	1777.7	0.02	1777.4
Mode 4	2541.2	0.07	2539.8	0.02	2539.3
Mode 5	2857.0	0.29	2851.3	0.09	2848.6
Mode 6	3421.7	0.03	3420.9	0.00	3420.8

where ω_{rot} and ω_{nr} are the rotating and non-rotating frequencies respectively, Ω is the blade rotational speed, and k is a constant known as Southwell’s coefficient (39). The gas loads arise due to the temperature and pressure field in the gas path of the engine and these are functions of the engine speed.

FIGURE 15: Modeshapes for first four modes

The stresses and displacements arising due to these loads must be accounted for while determining the frequencies in a rotating fan. The frequencies for the rotating fan are obtained in two steps. A static analysis is carried out at first to determine the stresses/displacements because of centrifugal force and gas loads. Subsequently, a modal analysis is carried out with added stiffness contributions from pre-existing loads calculated in the first step.

Structural dynamic analyses were carried out on a blade-only model since geometric details for the disk, on which the blades are mounted, are not available in the public domain. Twenty-noded quadratic solid elements were used for generating the structural mesh of an individual blade. The material properties of the NASA rotor 67 are not disclosed, and researchers have assumed

FIGURE 16: Campbell diagram

these properties to estimate its modal characteristics. We have assumed that the blade is made of titanium alloy, as most of the modern fans are made of the same material. For the chosen material, Young’s modulus is 1.172×10^{11} Pa, Poisson’s ratio is 0.3 and density is 4539 kg/m^3 . The gas loads from the steady flow solution corresponding to the OP2 operating point were mapped onto the structural mesh. The blade root was fixed. For the pre-stressed modal analysis, a block-shifted Lanczos algorithm (40) was used following a static pass.

A mesh sensitivity exercise was carried out using three meshes with node counts of 8145 (coarse), 15560 (medium), and 31823 (fine). The first six natural frequencies obtained using the three meshes are compared in Table 2. The errors in the natural frequencies for the coarse and medium meshes with respect to that for the fine mesh are also presented in Table 2. Comparing the first six natural frequencies obtained using the three meshes, the mesh with 15560 nodes—medium mesh—was found to be the optimal mesh, and all further structural analyses were performed using this mesh.

The first natural frequency at the design speed is found to be 537 Hz using the chosen (medium) mesh, which is in good agreement with that reported by (41; 42). The modeshapes corresponding to the first four modes are presented in Fig. 15. These normal modes correspond to the first flap mode, the second flap mode, the first torsion mode, and the first edgewise mode, respectively. A Campbell diagram is constructed by carrying out modal analyses at seven rotor speeds—0%, 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, 100% and 110%—in order to have an idea about possible engine order (EO) interferences. Note that, the blade geometry corresponding to the design speed is used to generate the interference diagram, and blade untwisting and change in gas loads due to change in

rotor speed are not accounted for here as that would be beyond the scope of this work. However, at the design speed, where the structural dynamic response is intended to be assessed, these aspects are accounted for. The Campbell diagram is shown in Fig. 16. The buffet frequencies corresponding to the two operating points—OP2 and OP3—reported earlier, are also shown in the Campbell diagram.

The two buffet frequencies—385 Hz at OP2 and 433 Hz at OP3—are not likely to excite any engine order which can be seen from the Campbell diagram. The closest natural frequency to the buffet frequencies is the first one—537 Hz—which is far off to be excited by the two buffet frequencies. In other words, the buffet flows at the two operating points do not induce buffeting in the fan. With this finding, the structural dynamic response of the fan to the unsteady buffet flow is assessed using transient structural analyses which are presented in the next section.

FIGURE 17: Unsteady pressure distribution on three consecutive blades, at the operating point near design mass flow, sampled at the buffet frequency.

FIGURE 18: Peak transient response (total deformation)

(a) LE and TE responses

(b) Mis-stagger response

FIGURE 19: Blade tip response and resulting mis-stagger response.

Aeromechanical response to buffet flow

The shocks in adjacent passages are found to be moving with almost out-of-phase motions with each other at this operating point. As a consequence of the out-of-phase motions of shocks in adjacent passages, the unsteady pressure distributions on adjacent blade surfaces also display similar phase differences. Fig. 17 shows the frequency contents of the unsteady pressure on three consecutive blades corresponding to the buffet frequency. From Fig. 17a, the unsteady pressure magnitudes on adjacent blades are seen to be similar, whereas Fig. 17b suggests an almost out-of-phase behavior of the unsteady pressure distribution in between adjacent blades.

FIGURE 20: DFT of blade tip deformation

FIGURE 21: DFT of blade tip mis-stagger

Fig. 18 shows the deformation pattern corresponding to the peak deformation from the transient response solution along with

FIGURE 22: Schematic of blade deformation pattern due to shock motion

the undeformed edges. The response is predominantly a flexural mode with a component of torsion at the buffet frequency which can be further ascertained from the undamped responses of the leading edge (LE) and trailing edge (TE) at the tip section shown in Fig. 19a. The resulting mis-staggering is shown in Fig. 19b. This kind of motion gives rise to a circumferential deformation with an amplitude of about 2.1% pitch (at leading edge location) associated with a tip mis-stagger with an amplitude of about 0.1° as seen from Fig. 19b.

Discrete Fourier transforms of the dynamic responses at the leading and trailing edge locations of the blade tip are carried out to investigate their frequency contents which are shown in Fig. 20. The buffet frequency of 385 Hz can be clearly seen from Fig. 20 to be the single driver of the responses corresponding to the leading and trailing edge locations on the blade tip section. The frequency contents in the mis-stagger response at the blade tip section, which was shown in Fig. 19b, are also investigated through a discrete Fourier transform of the corresponding signal which is shown in Fig. 21. The buffet frequency of 385 Hz clearly appears along with a small contribution of a frequency of 1781 Hz which is very close to the torsional normal mode frequency of 1778 Hz. So far, the dynamic response of an individual blade undergoing shock buffet has been analyzed. It would be interesting to see how adjacent blades respond with respect to each other in the unsteady flow field featuring shock buffet. A schematic of the deformation pattern in three consecutive blades, undergoing transient responses as described earlier, is presented in Fig. 22. The deformation of adjacent blades with out-of-phase unsteady loadings with respect to each other will give rise to an alternating pitch variation associated with an alternating mis-staggering wherein a blade passage is slightly stretched and converged, and

FIGURE 23: Instantaneous deformation pattern for three consecutive blades undergoing buffet

the adjacent one is slightly shrunk and diverged. To verify this assertion, unsteady pressure time histories over three consecutive blades are extracted and then transient structural responses of the three blades to the unsteady loadings are estimated. The transient structural responses of the three blades together can be visualized from the video in the presentation. An instantaneous snap of the deformation pattern from the transient structural simulation with the three blades considered is shown in Fig. 23. The deformation pattern shown in Fig. 22 is seen to be replicated by this exercise.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Modal analysis of buffet flow near design mass flow operating point of a transonic axial flow fan using SPOD clearly captures the buffet frequency as the dominant frequency. Just the most energetic SPOD mode in addition to the mean flow suffices for the reconstruction of the buffet flow. The flow structures near the shocks of adjacent passages corresponding to the dominant SPOD mode are found to be displaying a phase difference of about 180°. Further, pressure disturbances, associated with this SPOD mode, are found to be propagating circumferentially at part-speed of the fan in the spinning direction of the fan, and part of the circumferentially-propagating pressure waves downstream of the blade row is transformed into upstream-propagating waves inside the passages.

The buffet frequencies at the two operating points, which are far off the lowest natural frequency of the blade—determined from modal analysis—are unlikely to excite buffeting. The aeromechanical response of a blade-only model to the unsteady loading arising of shock buffet at design mass flow, assessed from a transient structural analysis, is a dominant flexural mode with a component of twist at the buffet frequency giving rise to a circumferential deformation with an amplitude up to 2.1% pitch associated with a mis-stagger. This kind of deformation on adjacent blades with almost out-of-phase unsteady loadings will give rise to an alternating pitch variation associated with an alternating mis-staggering wherein a blade passage is slightly stretched and converged, and the adjacent one is slightly shrunk and diverged.

And, this assertion is demonstrated with a transient structural analysis consisting of three consecutive blades. Shock buffet is shown to be a formidable driver for alternating pitch variation and alternating mis-staggering in fan blades. The aerodynamic mistuning induced by the buffet flow, in general, can influence the aerodynamic performance, aeroacoustic behavior, aeromechanical stability, and high cycle fatigue life of the fan.

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